

tervals. In the second year, sampling was done in different parts of the field. The thrips counts were transformed by square root transformation and single-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) was undertaken, considering panicles as replicates. Separate ANOVA were done for each sampling date during 1998.

The thrips population differed significantly among the three categories of panicles (see table). Freshly emerged

panicles harbored the most thrips, followed by emerging panicles and panicles in the milky stage. The panicle stage thus influenced thrips incidence. The study revealed that panicle thrips in rice first attacked the emerging panicles, continuing until the milky stage. Therefore, to prevent crop loss from thrips, control measures should be applied at the panicle initiation stage. Control measures at the milky stage would be useless because, at this stage, the

thrips population has almost disappeared and the crop has already been damaged.

The study also showed that freshly emerged panicles had the highest number of thrips among the three stages of panicle growth. Therefore, to correctly estimate the thrips population in rice, freshly emerged panicles should be sampled. Sampling on emerging panicles or panicles in the milky stage would underestimate the thrips population.

Further testing of a yield loss simulation model for rice in different production situations

I. FOCUS ON RICE-WHEAT SYSTEM ENVIRONMENTS

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A synthetic yield loss simulation model for rice pests was developed recently (Willocquet et al 1998) as a tool for setting research priorities and improving pest management. This model is production situation (PS)-specific and addresses several rice pests. It has been tested in several Asian PSs (e.g., in the Philippines and Vietnam), where it simulates attainable rice crop growth adequately as well as losses caused by various pests (diseases, insects, and weeds) (Willocquet et al 1998).

This work aimed at further testing of the model under a wider range of PS. The PSs and injuries addressed here were defined based on characterization of rice injury profiles and PSs across tropical Asia (Savary et al 1998). The first PS, PS2, is a reference used in all experiments. Two other PSs (PS8 and PS9) represent those prevailing in Uttar Pradesh (Savary et al 1997).

An experiment was done at NDUAT in the 1998 kharif season. In each PS, injury-free plots and rice plots injured by pests (alone or in combination) were established. Crop growth, environmental factors, and pest injuries were monitored throughout the growing season. In a given

PS, data from injury-free plots were used to calibrate parameters to simulate attainable yield. Data from injured plots were used to test simulations of yield losses. Three PSs were addressed: PS2 (IR72 transplanted with young seedlings, 110 kg N ha⁻¹, irrigated rice), PS8 (Sita transplanted with old seedlings, 100 kg N ha⁻¹, rainfed crop), and PS9 (direct-seeded NDR80, 80 kg N ha⁻¹, rainfed crop). Five injury treatments common in South Asia (Savary et al 1997) were established in each PS: sheath blight (SHB), deadhearts and whiteheads (DWH), brown spot (BS), the combination of the four injuries (COMBI), and the noninjured (CTRL) treatment. The injury treatments were randomized with three replications in each PS. Individual plots were 2.8 × 2.8 m and included four zones from the outer to the inner part of the plot: a border row, 20 cm wide; a sampling zone, 20 cm wide, to monitor crop growth (destructive samplings) and injuries; a second border row, 20 cm wide; and the central harvest area.

The simulation of attainable growth (leaf, stem, root, and panicle dry weight; and tiller population) and of final yield was close to observed values (see figure) in the

three PSs considered. In all PSs, the same patterns were observed: an increase in leaf weight until flowering, then a decline (leaf senescence); an increase in root weight until flowering, remaining stable afterwards; an increase in stem weight until flowering, then a decline (translocation of stored starch from stems to panicles); and an increase in panicle weight from flowering to maturity. Tillering occurred until 30 to 40 d after crop establishment (DACE). Tiller number declined afterwards because of tiller death and remained constant after flowering. The dry weights of leaves and panicles were very sensitive to varying PSs: the maximum values were highest in PS2 and lowest in PS8 and PS9 (shortage of water and/or N). Final yield varied between 151 g m⁻² (PS8) and 666 g m⁻² (PS2). Tiller number was higher in PS2 than in PS8 and PS9, mainly because of crop establishment method (young seedlings in PS2, older ones in PS8 and PS9).

The table shows the simulated and observed grain yields for the 15 (PS × injury) combinations addressed in the experiment. An acceptance interval of ± 10% of the observed grain yield was defined to assess the simulated yield outputs. The

Attainable rice growth in three production systems (PS): observed (dots) \pm SEM and simulated (plain line) dry weight (g m^{-2}) of roots (ROOTW), dry weight of leaves (LEAFW), dry weight of stems (STEMW), dry weight of panicles (PANW), and number (m^{-2}) of tillers (TOTIL). Observed data were collected from control plots in the experiment done at NDUAT in 1998 (A:PS2, B:PS8, C:PS9) (see text for details).

Simulated and observed grain yields (g m^{-2}), NDUAT, 1998.

Treatment ^a	PS2 ^b		PS8 ^b		PS9 ^b	
	Observed	Simulated ^c	Observed	Simulated	Observed	Simulated
CTRL	583	586	83	83	113	113
DWH	400	531 ^c	26	41 ^c	74	93 ^c
SHB	478	518	59	55	83	91
BS	544	469 ^c	66	51 ^c	81	68 ^c
COMBI	397	411	27	25	70	55 ^c

^aCTRL = control, DWH = deadhearts and whiteheads, SHB = sheath blight, BS = brown spot, and COMBI = combination of the four injuries. ^bPS2 = reference production situation, PS8 and PS9 = production situations that prevail in Uttar Pradesh. ^cSimulated grain yield is outside the acceptance interval ($\pm 10\%$ of observed grain yield).

model simulated yields within this acceptance interval in the SHB treatment and in the COMBI treatment (except in PS9). Injury because of whiteheads and deadhearts was underestimated by the model. Three areas for further improvement of deadheart injury modeling are (a) alteration of the dynamics of tillers: because of compensation mechanisms, more tillers are produced than in an uninjured crop; (b) most of these tillers that are produced at a late development stage remain veg-

etative and compete with the reproductive ones for assimilate partitioning, leading to a decrease in grain filling; (c) in “poor” PSs, such as PS8 and PS9, compensation mechanisms in terms of dry weight of organs are limited due to the unfavorable environment for rice growth. Yield losses from BS were slightly overestimated (see table). The damage mechanism function for BS was represented as a reduction in photosynthesis in the area surrounding the lesion. This area might be overestimated and

could be recalibrated using data from this experiment and tested in another independent experiment.

Although further improvements in this simulation model are necessary, it is flexible enough to account for diverse PSs and has the potential to reflect reasonably well the damage mechanisms due to various rice pests.

References

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